

THE HARMONY OF KNOWLEDGE, ENLIGHTENMENT AND UPBRINGING IN THE WORKS OF ABDULLA AVLONIY

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Abstract. *The given article briefly analyzes the role of enlightenment in the social views of the outstanding enlightener, talented poet and educator Abdulla Avloni, as well as his views on spiritual and educational education in the stories presented in his works such as “Turkiy Gulistan yoxud axloq”, “Birinchi muallim”, the importance of education in raising the spirituality of the nation, and issues such as raising the future generation as perfect human beings.*

Keywords: *education, morality, enlightenment, new school, perfect, young generation, spirituality, educational reforms, pedagogy, national values, national awakening, literary heritage, modern education, moral education.*

Introduction. It is important to suggest that in his works, Abdulla Avloniy reflects on ethics as “a knowledge that calls people to do good and warns them against evil.” His perspective on this subject is as follows: ethics is a set of behaviors, and such behavior—especially good character—does not appear in a person naturally or by itself. For these qualities to form, certain conditions and upbringing are required. People are not born evil; it is specific environments that shape them negatively.

In this regard, the role of schools and the dissemination of enlightenment among the people became the main direction of Avloniy’s activity as an educator and reformer. The school he opened in Mirobod gained great fame throughout Tashkent. In 1909, Avloniy opened another school in the Degrez neighborhood and realized the necessity of creating suitable textbooks for modern-style schools.

Between 1909 and 1917, he published several textbooks and literary collections, including “First Teacher,” “Second Teacher,” “Turkiy Guliston or Ethics,” “The School Garden”, and a six-part series titled “Literature or National Poems.” Avloniy’s pedagogical views are most clearly expressed in these works.

In 1913, his book “Turkiy Guliston or Ethics” was published. It was written as a textbook for upper-grade students, but it also served as a valuable guide for lovers of literature and ethics. In 1933, at a time when there were no textbooks or anthologies for the newly opened schools in the country, he compiled and published a “Literature Anthology” for 7th-grade students.

According to Avloniy, the progress of a nation and the strength of a state depend largely on the education of its younger generations. Speaking about the importance of upbringing, the author emphasizes:

“In short, for us, education is a matter of life or death, salvation or destruction, happiness or misery” [1]. The ideas he expressed are universal truths that apply to the upbringing of people from all nations. From these thoughts, it becomes clear that the education of an individual is not a private matter, but rather a social, national, and governmental responsibility.

Education begins the day a child is born and continues throughout their life.

In his book “The First Teacher”, in the story “Good Deeds Do Not Go Unnoticed,” Abdulla Avloniy talks about cooperation:

One day, a bee was flying and suddenly fell into the water, struggling to stay afloat. A pigeon, seeing this, threw a stick into the water to help. The bee managed to escape. By coincidence, one day a boy set a trap to catch the pigeon. The pigeon accidentally got caught in the trap. The boy hurried to take his prize, but the bee, having heard about the event, rushed to help. It arrived and stung the boy’s ear. The boy grabbed his ear with both hands, and the pigeon, freed from the trap, flew joyfully into the sky.

“If you do good, your soul will remain safe.

No one ever suffers from doing good.

A kind word can take a snake out of its hole,

But a harsh word can turn a knife into a sword.” [2]

Definitely, the “Second Teacher” is a direct continuation of “The First Teacher”, and it is “adorned with ethical stories and literary poems.” In this work, Avloniy places great emphasis on the stories being life-like and interesting, with simple and clear expression. He strives to write in “the easiest way” and with “clear language and simple structure.” As we read the book, we can clearly see that Avloniy skillfully uses the pearls of folk oral literature. Many of the stories are based on materials from this tradition.

In the story titled “Generosity”, an event characteristic of the time is depicted: A boy named Said’s father would give him 10 coins for food every day before he went to school. One day, Said meets a beggar on his way to school. The beggar says, “My son, I have been hungry for two days. I want food, but all I have is this torn cloak.” Said gives the beggar the 10 coins in his hand, and spends the day without food. His father is pleased with his son’s nobility and praises him, calling him “Generous Said!” The next day, the father gives Said 20 coins. In this story, generosity and compassion are depicted as virtues, while “stinginess” is condemned. In the story “Greed”, miserly behavior and narrow-mindedness are criticized.

In the stories and fables like “Smart Boy”, “Cabbage and Wild Spinach”, “Voice”, “The Fox and the Wolf”, and “The Curse of Greed” (from the same book, page 113), wisdom, kindness, good manners, and the importance of helping others are praised as human virtues. Intelligence and wisdom are honored, while vices such as rudeness and selfishness are satirized. For example, in the story “Smart Boy”, the benefits of quick wit and cleverness, as well as the importance of acting wisely, are demonstrated through a small narrative.

In the story “The Harm of Quarrelling”, the negative consequences of arrogance and stubbornness are conveyed through a brief, impactful event: a long board is placed over a large canal. Two goats meet at the same time and do not want to let each other pass. The situation escalates to a struggle, and both fall into the water. (from the same book, pp. 220–221).

In the fables “False Friend” and “True Friend”, special attention is given to the important issue of friendship in human life. Avloniy emphasizes that true friendship starts in youth and stresses the necessity of instilling these qualities in a child from an early age.

In “The Second Teacher”, Avloniy pays particular attention to the issue of labor. According to him, work is not some unnatural power that brings happiness and fame; rather, work is simply work. Therefore, it requires strength and willpower, and it is an activity that tires and challenges a person.

In "The Disaster of Ignorance", Abdulla Avloniy condemns ignorance and praises knowledge and enlightenment, warning that ignorance can lead a person to tragedy.

Methodology. Avloniy understood education in a broad sense, not limiting it solely to ethics. He knew well that the proverb "A healthy body is the foundation for a healthy mind" was not without reason. He cares about a child's health. According to him, a healthy and strong body is essential because it is necessary for reading, learning, and teaching.

Avloniy's thoughts on conscience are also noteworthy. He writes: "Conscience is the moral strength that influences our soul and mind. We are always aware of the goodness or badness, the benefits or harms of our actions through our mind and conscience. Conscience is the true standard of human reasoning, by which we measure our own shortcomings and sense the actions of others. If one's actions are in accordance with circumstances, intellect, and wisdom, they will be loved. If they perform disgraceful and harmful actions, they will be hated..."

Conscience is the source of good deeds, and those who possess a clear conscience perform every action with selfless, pure intentions. For this reason, they are seen as admirable and beloved by all. In the end, conscience is like a clear mirror that reflects a person's actions, allowing them to see their own faults and shortcomings. When one looks into this mirror with a sincere heart, they will focus on correcting their own flaws rather than searching for the faults of others. (from the same book, pp. 258-259). Avloniy says that the true measure of upbringing is conscience.

The feeling of patriotism is one of the most human and honorable emotions. Living with the pain of one's homeland, sharing in its joy, and feeling pride for it is essential. The homeland is sacred, like a mother. Respecting and honoring it, sharing its happiness and joy, and participating in its sorrow and grief is the duty of every child. Avloniy understands patriotism and one's duty toward their country in this way. He says:

"Each person's birthplace and homeland is considered their homeland. Every person loves the land they were born and raised in more than anything else. Even animals have this sense of homeland. If an animal is separated from its home or den, it cannot live in peace and comfort like it did in its homeland. Its life becomes bitter, and in the back of its mind, the love for its homeland remains." (from the same book, p. 259).

Results and discussion. Children also come in different forms accordingly. Some share in their mother's happiness, while others may leave her lonely in her sorrow. There are children who only love the beautiful nature and gardens of the homeland but do not think about its struggles and sorrows. Regardless of what the homeland may be, it must be loved.

"We, the people of Turkestan," says Avloniy, "love our homeland more than our own lives. Just as Arabs love Arabia, with its hot deserts, or Eskimos love the northern lands, with their cold and icy territories, more than any other places. If they did not love them, they would have abandoned their homeland for places with better climates and easier living conditions. Our ancestors said, 'Better to be a shepherd in your own land than a sultan in another country.'" (from the same book, p. 255).

Love for language and culture is the love each person has for their nation: "The life of a nation, which shows its existence in the world, is reflected through its language and literature," writes the author.

Avloniy evaluates the role of language in determining a person's dignity from a universal human perspective. Continuing with universal ideas about the etiquette of words, he states: "...words are the scales that measure a person's rank and perfection, their knowledge and virtue.

A wise person's thoughts, intentions, knowledge, and worth can be known from the words they speak..."

In his stories, Avloniy praises truthfulness and honesty as among the most human qualities.

"Truthfulness refers to correctness in action and honesty in speech. A person will find the path to health and happiness through truthfulness. The roots of humanity, such as kindness, justice, and righteousness, are all born from truthfulness..." (from the same book, pp. 260-261), emphasizes the author.

Encouraging people towards goodness, warning them away from evil, and living with the wish for kindness towards all human beings is true nobility. People live in constant connection with each other throughout their lives, always needing help and cooperation. Therefore, benevolence and nobility hold significant importance in human life.

Conclusion. Avloniy dedicated all his strength, creativity, and life to the happiness and well-being of his people. He fulfilled his filial duties to his homeland with honor. He made a significant contribution to the development of Uzbek pedagogy. In this sense, personality and activities of Avloniy are invaluable to us.

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